

The Phenomenon of Deep Nudes – a New Threat to Children and Adults

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Abstract

The article explores the misuse of artificial intelligence (AI) to generate pornographic images, including child pornography, through so-called deep nudes - applications that create realistic nude images from photographs without the consent of individuals. This phenomenon has serious psychological and social impacts on victims, especially children, who can become targets of cyberbullying, blackmail and other forms of abuse. The paper presents the results of a survey on the use of artificial intelligence among Czech primary and secondary school students (2024), which involved over 27,336 respondents. Deep nude photos with the help of AI were created by 2.77% of Czech primary and secondary school pupils. Deep nude is more likely to be generated by boys, who are 3.56 times more likely to generate a deep nude photo than girls. There are also differences based on age and type of school, but these differences are negligible.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, deep nudes, child pornography

1 Introduction

In recent years, with the rapid development of technology and Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI)(Giannini, 2023; Lyu, 2023), new challenges and threats have emerged that require a thorough analysis and response from society. In the online space, users are encountering, for example, deep fake photos and videos, cloned voices, AI-generated disinformation texts, online fraud (Europol, 2024; Kopecký et al., 2024; Kopecký & Szotkowski, 2024) and other products created through AI tools. In several cases, these tools involve children and their abuse (CSAM). According to the Internet Watch Foundation (IWF), there has been a dramatic increase in this type of content (IWF, 2024), which is more sophisticated and is actively disseminated by the Internet.

One of the most serious and morally problematic aspects of this issue is the misuse of artificial intelligence tools to create child pornography or any other pornography in which, for example, adults' faces are replaced with children's faces (face swapping). This phenomenon not only constitutes a violation of fundamental human rights and dignity but also endangers the safety and psychological development of children. In the context of this article, we will focus on the mechanisms by which artificial intelligence contributes to the production of such content, and the ethical, legal and social implications of this abuse. In particular, we will focus on the issue of so-called deep nudes.

1.1 *The phenomenon of deep nudes*

The term deep nudes (AI deep nude, AI fake nude, deep fake pornography, etc.) is a term for sexually explicit (often pornographic) realistic photographs/images of people that have been created using AI tools. These tools can remove clothing from photographs or videos of people, generate a nude human body and create a realistic illusion of nudity. (Kopecký, 2024; Van de Heyning et al., 2023). Another possibility is to generate a completely new digital undressed

figure that is indistinguishable from a real person. The tools that make this possible are freely available and can be misused by literally anyone.

To create this type of material, all that is needed is a regular photograph of the person in question, who may be fully clothed. Most of the available apps do not contain ethical limits with respect to age - they will equally generate a photo of a child, an adult woman or a senior citizen. There are many applications that allow you to create deep nude materials¹, for example Undress.cc, UndressAI.Tools, AI-Nudes, Candy AI, Clothoff, etc. In most cases, they are freely available - either completely free or in paid versions.

Figure 1

Example of a Generated Nude Photo of an Underage Girl Using www.deepnude.cc app (Source: E-safety, 2024)

Note. To comply with ethical standards and privacy regulations, the image was not created from a real person's photograph. Instead, the original photo was synthetically generated using artificial intelligence and subsequently modified with a deep nude application.

1.2 Incidence of deep nudes in Europe and the USA

There are still very few studies mapping the prevalence of deep nudes in Europe or the USA, so there is no accurate data on how many children have experienced deep nudes either as victims or perpetrators. On the other hand, the number of cases recorded by the police in which AI has been used to generate sensitive material of a sexual nature is increasing, according to Europol (Europol, 2024).

¹ Some applications of this type cannot generate undressed men because they are trained on female photos. When trying to generate men, they then generate men with female sex instead of penises.

One study conducted in Belgium (Van de Heyning et al., 2023) focused on the phenomenon of deep nudes among young people aged 15-25 years. It found that 41.9% had heard of deep nudes and 23.1% had seen them, most often on social media such as Snapchat or Twitter. Men are more likely to be involved in watching, creating and keeping them. The research also showed that 12.8% of respondents are familiar with apps for creating deep nudes, with 60.5% having actively used these apps. The study calls for greater regulation and awareness to counter this form of digital sexual violence.

In the USA, research has already been conducted in 2023 on the issue of deep fakes (Home Security Heroes, 2023). This identified a dramatic increase in deep fake pornography, which accounted for over 98% of all deepfake videos, with 99% of the people depicted in these videos being women. The report also points out that it took less than 25 minutes to create a 60-second video in 2023, and often only one photo was needed to create it.

1.3 Target of abuse - children, but also famous personalities

Celebrities (singers, actors, presenters, etc.) are very often the target of deep fake pornography, with their faces being unethically inserted into erotic/pornographic material through advanced artificial intelligence algorithms, completely without their knowledge or permission.

An investigation ((Badshah, 2024) revealed nearly 4,000 celebrity victims, including British actresses, musicians and TV stars. Victims, such as Channel 4 presenter Cathy Newman, describe this invasion of privacy as deeply humiliating and disturbing. Although the law in the UK prohibits the dissemination of such material, its production remains unregulated - as in other countries.

Singer Taylor Swift, for example, had also an experience with AI-generated pornography (AP News, 2024; Tenbarga, 2024). On Wednesday, January 24, 2024, sexually explicit deep fakes photos of her created by artificial intelligence went viral on Network X (formerly Twitter), garnering over 27 million views and more than 260,000 likes in 19 hours before the account that posted the images was suspended. Deep fakes depicting Swift naked and in sex scenes have been steadily spreading through the X network and other social media sites.

Figure 2

Sexually Explicit Image of Taylor Swift Generated by AI (cropped)

Unfortunately, it is not only celebrities who have experience with deep nude material. Increasingly, children are trying out deep nude apps - boys, for example, are creating undressed photos of their classmates from photos posted on Instagram and other social networks. Politicians also have a problem with deep fake pornography (Döll, 2024)- especially women, who are frequent targets of AI tools. It can even be said that AI can disrupt democratic processes, e.g. by dehumanising political opponents in this way.

2 Cases from the school environment

2.1 Europe

Among the first cases captured in Europe is the case of the abuse of photographs of 20 girls aged 11 to 17 from Almendralejo, Spain (Llach, 2023), which were downloaded from their Instagram profile, re-created using a deep nude app and disseminated through WhatsApp groups. One of the girls was then even blackmailed that if she did not pay, her intimate photo would be published. Other cases have been reported from Germany (Breschendorf, 2024), Poland and the UK.

Cases of a similar type are also dealt with by the Czech police (iDNES.cz, 2023; Kulasová, 2023) or the Czech E-Safety project counselling centre www.napisnam.cz, which schools can contact anonymously, however, these are isolated cases. The reported incidents look very similar - pupils (boys) discover the existence of a stripping app, download intimate photos of their female classmates from their Instagram profiles, for example, and create a deep nude. They then spread them among their classmates.

2.2 USA

As in Europe, cases of deepfake nude are also occurring in the US - The New York Times (*Teen Girls Confront an Epidemic of Deepfake Nudes in Schools - The New York Times*, n.d.) recently highlighted the appearance of photos of undressed female students, created by artificial intelligence, wandering through several schools in the US (Westfield Public Schools in New Jersey). The schools launched an investigation and informed the police about the situation. The police have repeatedly warned that the creation and distribution of such material among adolescents is illegal and that such cases must be reported. It was subsequently discovered that the production and distribution of deep fake photos was perpetrated by a student who struck up a friendship with a 15-year-old classmate on Instagram, copied their photos from her account (and those of other classmates) and created deep nudes, which he then used Snapchat to spread among his classmates.

Issaquah High School near Seattle also experienced a proliferation of sexually explicit material targeting 14- and 15-year-old students. The school failed to report the incident to the police, despite being legally obligated to do so, as the creation of such content constitutes a form of sexual abuse under applicable law. Deep Nudes was also dealt with by Beverly Vista High School in Beverly Hills, California - five boys created and shared explicit images of female classmates created by artificial intelligence. The boys were subsequently expelled. In addition, the school published a statement saying that "Any student found to create, distribute, or possess images created by AI of this nature will face disciplinary action - including a recommendation for expulsion". Other cases have emerged, for example, at Richmond Burton High School in

Illinois (Nguyen, 2024), in which over 30 female students and 3 female teachers at the school were victims of deep nude

3 Methods

3.1 Research tool and data collection

For this study, a unique online questionnaire was created using Google Forms. It was distributed via email to teachers at all primary and secondary schools across the Czech Republic. Participation in the research was voluntary. Teachers were responsible for deciding whether to participate with their students. In the Czech educational system, schools typically obtain general parental consent at the beginning of the school year, which might include permission for students to take part in educational research. Teachers were instructed to administer the questionnaire only if such consent had been obtained. The data collection was fully anonymous and did not involve any personally identifiable or sensitive information.

Data were collected between September 2 and December 5, 2024. In total, 28,745 students submitted responses. The dataset was cleaned by excluding responses from participants outside the target population, specifically university-level respondents and those younger than 10 years. The final dataset comprised 27,336 valid responses. The data were processed using the Python programming language, utilizing the pandas library for data manipulation and matplotlib for data visualization. Descriptive and inferential statistical analyses were performed using standard non-parametric tests.

3.2 Survey structure

The survey was structured into several thematic sections, focusing on different aspects of the use of generative artificial intelligence (AI) by students. Sections of the questionnaire were as follows: demographic information, generative AI in leisure time, AI use in education and AI in future, special part of survey was focused on misuse of AI by students (cyberbullying, deep nude, deep fake etc.).

3.3 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

The final dataset included respondents aged 10 to 18 years. Female respondents made up 51.79%, and male respondents accounted for 48.21%.

The age distribution of the sample was analyzed to assess adherence to a normal distribution. The mean age was 14.18 years (SD = 1.99), with minimal skewness (0.05) and negative kurtosis (-0.65), suggesting a relatively flat distribution. Shapiro-Wilk and Anderson-Darling tests rejected the null hypothesis of normality ($p < 0.001$), but visual inspection of histograms (Figure 2) indicated a distribution close to normality for practical purposes.

Figure 3

Age Distribution of Respondents

n = 27 336

In terms of geographical distribution, the sample covered all 14 administrative regions of the Czech Republic. The Central Bohemian Region had the highest representation, with 3,993 respondents (14.61% of the sample), followed by the Moravian-Silesian Region (11.35%) and the South Moravian Region (11.31%). Together, these three regions accounted for 37.27% of all responses. The capital city of Prague represented 10.09% of the sample, while the Karlovy Vary Region was the least represented, with 225 respondents (0.82%).

Together, these top three regions represent more than a third (37.27%) of all respondents. The capital city of Prague accounts for 10.09% of respondents, making it the fifth most represented region. The least represented region is Karlovy Vary with only 225 respondents (0.82% of the total).

Although the sample was not randomly selected and participation depended on the voluntary involvement of teachers and schools, the demographic characteristics—particularly gender, age, and regional distribution—suggest a reasonably balanced and diverse dataset. Minor overrepresentation of certain regions (e.g., Central Bohemia) and underrepresentation of smaller ones (e.g., Karlovy Vary) were noted, yet the sample still provides a valuable cross-sectional insight into the student population across the Czech Republic. These factors enhance the interpretability of the findings, while the non-random sampling method and potential self-selection bias should be considered as limitations when generalizing the results.

In addition to demographic and regional representation, the dataset also reflects a diverse range of school types. Most respondents were students attending primary schools. Specifically, the category “Primary School (1st–5th grade) / Lower Secondary School (6th–9th grade)” included 16,401 participants, representing exactly 60% of the total sample. This indicates that most of the data reflect the experiences of pupils in the primary education sector.

The second largest group consisted of students enrolled in Secondary Vocational Schools with a School-Leaving Certificate (maturita), comprising 4,967 respondents (18.17%). Grammar

schools were also represented: Eight-Year Grammar Schools accounted for 2,377 students (8.7%), and Four-Year Grammar Schools for 2,018 students (7.38%), amounting to approximately 16% of the total sample. Students from Secondary Vocational Schools with an Apprenticeship Certificate made up 3.62% of the sample (n = 990), while Six-Year Grammar Schools accounted for 1.81% (n = 494). The smallest category, labeled “Other,” included only 89 respondents (0.33%).

These figures reflect the structure of the Czech education system, which consists of several distinct educational pathways. Primary education is typically provided within a single institutional framework known as *základní škola*, encompassing both the initial stage (grades 1–5) and the lower secondary stage (grades 6–9). Upon completing this level, students transition to upper secondary education, which offers different tracks depending on academic orientation and career aspirations.

Grammar schools (*gymnázium*) represent academically selective institutions aimed at preparing students for higher education. These schools are structured into various programs based on the age of entry: Eight-Year Grammar Schools begin after grade 5, Six-Year Grammar Schools after grade 7, and Four-Year Grammar Schools after grade 9. All of these culminate in the national *maturita* examination, which qualifies graduates for university admission.

Secondary Vocational Schools (*střední odborná škola*), by contrast, emphasize professional training and practical skills. Some of these schools also prepare students for the *maturita*, combining vocational and general education. Others focus solely on hands-on training and award an Apprenticeship Certificate (*výuční list*), typically after a three-year program, without automatically granting access to tertiary education. However, further study is possible for those who wish to pursue the *maturita* subsequently.

4 Results

In our research, we primarily focused on three variables - age, gender, and type of school - to identify the characteristics prevalent among students who generate deep nude content. It was not specifically examined whom the children "undressed" using AI, whether it involved girls or boys, classmates, or others, nor was not investigated the motivation behind such behavior (this study is part of a broader research project exploring both the negative and positive aspects of this phenomenon). However, based on documented and analyzed case studies, it can be inferred that in most cases, the generated images likely involved unclothed classmates, primarily girls. Given the novelty of this phenomenon, we opted for an exploratory research approach. Rather than formulating specific hypotheses, this study is designed with the aim of gaining new insights and understanding.

From the entire research sample, 758 children (2.77%) reported creating deep nude photographs or videos. Boys were significantly overrepresented in this group, comprising 76.25% of those who generated deep nude content, while girls accounted for 23.75%.

Although no specific hypotheses were formulated in advance, statistical analysis using a chi-square test revealed a highly significant difference between boys and girls ($\chi^2(1) = 244.39$, $p < 0.001$, $V = 0.0946$), suggesting a strong association between gender and the likelihood of generating deep nude content. Standardized residuals (± 15.67) further reveal that boys generate deep nude photographs significantly more often than expected under random distribution. Conversely, for girls, this probability is significantly lower than what would be expected by chance.

Among 13,179 boys in the sample, 578 (4.39%) reported generating deep nude photographs. In contrast, only 180 (1.27%) of the 14,157 girls admitted to the same behaviour. Thus, boys are 3.56 times more likely to generate deep nude photographs compared to girls.

Figure 4

Distribution of Deep Nude Material Creation by Age and Gender

The Kruskal-Wallis test revealed statistically significant differences between age groups ($H = 23.75$, $p = 0.0025$). As part of the post-hoc analysis, Mann-Whitney U tests with Bonferroni correction were employed, adjusting the significance threshold to $\alpha = 0.00139$. Based on this adjustment, two statistically significant differences between the examined age groups were identified. The first was between the 12- and 14-year-old age groups ($p = 0.00018$), with an effect size indicated by Cliff's Delta of -0.0137 , representing a negligible effect. The second difference was between the 12- and 17-year-old age groups ($p = 0.00094$), with a Cliff's Delta of -0.0140 , also indicating a negligible effect. A percentage-based visualization of deep nude generation across age groups is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5

Percentage of Children Generating Deepnude by Age

As illustrated in Figure 6, the highest percentage of students who generated deep nude photographs was observed in secondary schools offering vocational certificates, whereas the lowest percentage was found in grammar schools. The analysis of deep nude generation across different school types revealed statistically significant differences, as indicated by the Kruskal-Wallis test ($H = 84.18$, $p < 0.0001$).

Figure 6

Percentage of Children Generating Deep Nude by School Type

n = 990-16,401

Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Mann-Whitney U tests with Bonferroni correction ($\alpha = 0.005$) identified significant differences between several pairs of school types, including Primary vs. Grammar Schools, Primary vs. Secondary Schools with Vocational Certificates, among others. However, the effect sizes, measured using Cliff's Delta, were consistently negligible ($|\Delta| < 0.147$). This indicates that while the differences are statistically significant, their practical significance is minimal. Details of these findings are presented in figure 7.

Figure 7

Post-hoc Pairwise Comparisons between Different Types of Schools

Comparison	P-Value	Cliff's Delta	Effect Size
Primary vs Grammar	< 0.00001	0,0151	negligible
Primary vs Secondary w/certificate	< 0.00001	-0,0276	negligible
Grammar vs Secondary w/exam	0.00018	-0,0106	negligible
Grammar vs Secondary w/certificate	< 0.00001	-0,0426	negligible
Secondary w/exam vs Secondary w/certificate	< 0.00001	-0,032	negligible

(n=758)

Since it is known that boys are more likely to generate deep nude images than girls, any comparison across different school types must consider the gender distribution within those schools. Our analysis revealed statistically significant differences in the prevalence of deep nude image generation among boys attending various types of secondary schools. The highest proportion of boys reporting the generation of such images was observed in Secondary Vocational Schools with an Apprenticeship Certificate, where 7.26% of them indicated having

generated deep nudes. In contrast, the lowest proportion was found among students attending Grammar Schools, with only 3.05% of boys reporting this behavior.

Although these differences are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), the effect size, as measured by Cliff's delta, is very small. The effect size between Secondary Vocational Schools with an Apprenticeship Certificate and Grammar Schools is 0.0421, which is categorized as a negligible effect. Similarly, the difference between Apprenticeship Certificate schools and Secondary Vocational Schools with a School-Leaving Examination (Maturita) yields a Cliff's delta of just 0.0278.

5 Discussion and recommendations

Since this is a new phenomenon, the issue of deep nude photography has not been sufficiently explored yet, and so we can only compare our results with a few studies. The results of our study, which focused on Czech primary and secondary school students, show that 2.77% of respondents created deep nude photos using AI, with boys being 3.56 times more prone to this behavior compared to girls. This study extends the findings of a Belgian research (Szyf et al., 2023), which found that 12.8% of young people aged 15-25 are familiar with deep nudes creation apps, of which 60.5% have actively used them. Belgian research also highlights gender inequalities, with men more likely to create and watch deep nudes, while girls and women are more likely to be victims. Similar results are reported in UK research (Internet Matters, 2024) which states that 13% of UK teenagers have experienced deep nude material, with male teenagers twice as likely to be the authors of such content as their female peers. Similar to our study, this shows a higher involvement of boys as creators of deep nudes, while girls are more likely to be victims.

Despite the finding that differences between school types are negligible, it is worth noting that the highest percentage of students who reported generating deep nude images was found among students attending Secondary Vocational Schools with an Apprenticeship Certificate — even when considering boys only. These schools are not academically oriented but rather focused on preparing students for direct entry into specific occupations (e.g., auto mechanic, waiter, cook). Unlike other secondary school types, they do not culminate in a school-leaving examination (*Maturita*), which would qualify students for higher education. This characteristic is important when considering the relationship between risk behavior and educational attainment. Baumgartner et al., (2012) found that adolescents with lower levels of education are significantly more likely to engage in both online (OnSRB) and offline (OffSRB) sexual risk behaviors. In their four-wave longitudinal study, students enrolled in lower educational tracks were more frequently represented in the moderate- and high-risk groups. Lower educational attainment emerged as one of the key predictors, alongside factors such as high sensation seeking, low life satisfaction, weak family cohesion, and frequent online communication. The authors emphasize that these students often lack sufficient support from both their families and the educational system, which makes them more vulnerable to risky behaviors.

5.1 *Effects of deep nude on child users*

The misuse of artificial intelligence technology to create deep nudes has several serious consequences for victims, especially when minors are involved. These impacts are complex and affect various aspects of victims' lives (American Academy of Pediatrics, 2024). From a psychological perspective, victims may experience intense trauma and emotional stress, associated with feelings of shame, anxiety and fear. Fake nude images can significantly undermine an individual's self-concept and self-esteem, negatively affecting their perception of their own body and identity. This can lead to depression and social isolation, with victims withdrawing from social interactions for fear of exposure or ridicule. Long-term consequences can also include a loss of trust in interpersonal relationships. The social impacts are equally serious. The spread of fake nude images can lead to reputational damage, social ostracism and (cyber)bullying. In the case of incidents in the school environment, the educational process can be disrupted, with attendance and concentration problems. There is also a risk of long-term consequences for future careers, especially if there is a wider dissemination of material.

From a legal and security perspective, victims are at risk of extortion (sextortion) and further victimization (Dearden, 2024). Remediation is also problematic, as removing objectionable content from the Internet can be almost impossible in practice. The effects are not lost on the victim's family and close circle. Parents and siblings may experience secondary trauma and the whole situation may lead to a breakdown in family relationships, especially when sensitive issues of sexuality are involved.

In a broader social context, the spread of these practices may lead to the normalization of sexual abuse and a blunting of social sensitivity to the issue. Given that the majority of victims are girls and women, this phenomenon may further exacerbate gender inequality and reinforce unwanted stereotypes.

Technological impacts include a potential loss of trust in digital media. The proliferation of deep fakes/deep nudes may lead to a general scepticism about the authenticity of digital content. This also creates the need for new security measures - schools and institutions need to implement new strategies to prevent and address these incidents.

5.2 Recommendations - school environment

In the event of so-called *deep nudes*, i.e. fake intimate photos created by artificial intelligence, appearing at school, it is essential to react quickly and in an organised manner. Such photo montages pose a serious threat to the psychological well-being and confidence of pupils in the school environment, as they can lead to feelings of shame, fear and humiliation. Moreover, thanks to advanced technology, there is now a danger that manipulated photographs can spread at the speed of viral content on social media and in private messages.

Once a person becomes aware of such content, it is crucial to prevent its further dissemination in the first place. The school should ask the IT administrator to block access to the files in question on school systems and ask pupils to stop forwarding the photos immediately. At the same time, evidence (e.g. screenshots, links, digital footprints) should be preserved for possible investigation. An important principle is the prudent handling of this material - it must be secured and not be further disseminated to teachers or pupils.

The Headmaster or Headmistress should then be informed immediately to determine the next course of action. It is recommended to convene a crisis team consisting of the school management, the educational counsellor, the school psychologist and, if necessary, the prevention methodologist. Their task is to ensure that psychological support is provided to the affected pupils and that further steps are coordinated, including discussions with parents or possible contact with the police.

In more serious cases, the creation and distribution of deep nudes may constitute a criminal offence or misdemeanour (e.g. production and distribution of child pornography, cyberbullying, defamation or invasion of privacy). It is advisable to consult the situation with the school's lawyer and to consider reporting to the Police. The school also has a reporting obligation if there is a suspected violation involving minors, including possible cooperation with a child welfare agency.

A key part of the procedure is to provide assistance and protection to pupils who are victims of such behaviour. The school should provide a safe space for them to express their concerns and offer psychological support - for example, through the school psychologist or by referring them

to specialist crisis lines. It is also important to be transparent with parents about what has happened, how the school is dealing with the situation and how parents can support their children during this difficult time.

For students who have participated in the creation or dissemination of deep nudes, it is necessary to determine the extent of their actions individually. In some cases they may be the authors of the photo montages, in others those who have spread them. The school should initiate a thorough conversation involving the parents where the seriousness of the conduct and its possible legal and ethical implications are clearly explained. Disciplinary measures (e.g. reprimand by the class teacher, reduced behavioural grades) may then be imposed in accordance with the applicable school rules, or criminal liability may arise for older pupils who have reached the age of 15 (age limits vary in European countries).

In order to prevent such situations, it is essential to include topics such as digital safety, media literacy and the ethics of using AI. In subjects such as computer science, civics or media education, students should acquire a critical approach to digital content and understand the dangers of advanced technologies. It is also important to build a positive school climate and promote open communication between pupils, teachers and parents - all of which help to identify early and effectively address signs of bullying or risky behaviour.

5.3 Recommendations for parents

Parents play a crucial role in shaping the values, attitudes, and behaviours of their children in relation to modern technologies (Álvarez-García et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2023). From an early age, they can guide their children towards respectful interactions with others, responsible online behaviour, and an understanding of the risks associated with digital content. Open dialogue within the family is an essential component of prevention. Regular conversations about children's online activities, their communication partners, and the content they access contribute to the creation of a climate of trust in which the child feels safe to share concerns or negative experiences.

It is important for parents to provide age-appropriate explanations that the creation or distribution of intimate content involving others - even if digitally altered or intended as a joke - can have serious ethical and legal consequences. Furthermore, fostering empathy in children and encouraging the ability to consider the perspective of those targeted by online aggression, such as cyberbullying (whether it involves deep nudes), is essential. Education should also include the development of digital literacy—an understanding of how digital technologies and artificial intelligence operate, why not everything encountered online is true, and the importance of handling sensitive information with care.

If a child confides that they have been a victim or witness of deep nude dissemination, it is vital to respond with calmness and support. The child must not be blamed but rather assured that they can turn to their parents for help. The matter should then be addressed promptly in cooperation with the school. If there is suspicion that the child was involved in the creation or distribution of such content, it is important to ascertain the extent of their involvement, engage in a patient conversation, and explain the seriousness of such actions. When necessary, professional support should be sought - for example, from a school psychologist or a prevention specialist.

Parents should also take an active interest in how schools address digital safety and media education. They are encouraged to support the school's preventive efforts and participate in workshops, lectures, or discussions offered by the institution. Collaboration between family and school is key to establishing a safe environment in which children understand the boundaries of online behaviour, are aware of potential risks, and know they can confidently seek support from trusted adults in the event of a threat.

5.4 Deep Nudes and Other Cyber Risks

It can be assumed that AI applications capable of generating "deep nudes" (as well as related tools such as deep swap or face swap) will increasingly be misused in the future as part of existing forms of cyberattacks targeting children. This is particularly likely in the context of cyberbullying and its various manifestations (e.g., body shaming) (Brigham et al., 2024), sextortion (i.e., blackmail involving intimate materials (Canadian Centre for Child Protection, 2017; Kopecký, 2014; Patchin & Hinduja, 2020), revenge porn (where materials are exploited by former partners to harm the victim's reputation) (Bates, 2017; Walker & Sleath, 2017), and cyber grooming in which intimate content is frequently used to manipulate a child into meeting the offender in person (Isaza et al., 2022; Webster et al., 2012; Whittle et al., 2013).

A major concern is that AI significantly simplifies the process of attacking a child or adult. In the past, obtaining sensitive material required time - particularly in cases of cyber grooming, which could involve months of psychological manipulation to gain the victim's trust. Today, sensitive content can be fabricated instantly from an ordinary photograph—or even just a facial image - using deep swap technology. Likewise, offenders previously needed a certain level of digital literacy (e.g., for editing or retouching images); this is no longer the case, as AI automates such processes.

Another critical issue is that large language models (LLMs) are highly proficient at mimicking diverse types of communication across languages. This enables potential offenders to easily overcome language barriers, allowing their interactions with victims to appear fluent and convincing. Moreover, AI tools can automatically adapt to the linguistic style of the child being targeted. It is also technically feasible to train AI to simulate manipulative techniques commonly used in grooming (Kopecký, 2015; Wachs et al., 2012), such as mirroring or luring. Although currently available public models (e.g., ChatGPT, Gemini, Copilot, Grok) have built-in ethical safeguards, these can often be circumvented through sophisticated prompt engineering.

On the other hand, it should be noted that such technologies (particularly deep nude generators) are relatively new and not yet widely adopted. Additionally, most tools used to generate deep nude content are monetized, which may limit their accessibility to children. Nevertheless, many of these services offer free trials, such as the ability to generate one image per day without charge.

These developments fundamentally reshape the requirements for effective primary prevention of risky online behavior. At present, most educators responsible for prevention activities (e.g., school prevention specialists, social educators, guidance counselors, school psychologists) lack sufficient knowledge about the risks posed by AI misuse. Therefore, education in this area is essential - for all relevant target groups, including students, parents, educators, psychologists, law enforcement officers, and other specialists.

Apart from education and parental guidance of child's online activities, a broader legal framework is essential to effectively address the systemic challenges posed by deepfake technologies. The new EU AI Act (European Parliament, 2023; Kurunsaari, 2024) introduces a definition of deepfake and imposes transparency obligations on the creators and users of AI systems generating such content. Another important step is the forthcoming directive on combating violence against women (European Parliament, 2024), which would criminalise the dissemination of non-consensual sexual deepfakes in all EU Member States. Current legislation, including the GDPR and the DSA (Booth, 2024; Costantini et al., 2018), provides some protection, but experts point to the need for more specific and stringent measures.

An example of legislative changes at the level of individual EU countries can be found in the draft of a new section of the Criminal Code of the Czech Republic (Svorník, 2024) entitled *"Abuse of identity for the production of pornography and its dissemination"*. The draft states that *whoever produces or distributes pornographic work that depicts or otherwise exploits a person who has not consented to it will be punished by imprisonment for up to two years, prohibition of activity or confiscation of property. If he or she publishes such material, for example on the internet, he or she faces a prison sentence of six months to three years. If he does so as part of an organised group in several countries or if he seeks to obtain large-scale benefits for himself in this way, he will lose his freedom for one to five years.* If lawmakers adopt an amendment to the section, it should come into force in July 2025.

6 Conclusion

The phenomenon of AI-generated deep nudes represents a growing threat to the safety and well-being of both children and adults, and poses profound ethical, legal, psychological, and educational challenges. This study, based on a large-scale quantitative survey among Czech primary and secondary school students, contributes to a better understanding of how this phenomenon manifests within the school environment. The findings reveal that 2.77% of respondents admitted to creating deep nude images using AI technologies, with boys being significantly more likely than girls to engage in this behavior. Although statistical analyses confirmed differences across school types and age groups, the practical significance of these differences was negligible. However, the observed differences between types of schools suggest that individuals with lower levels of education may constitute a more vulnerable group in terms of risky online behaviour. Future educational policies should therefore prioritise non-academic educational pathways.

Despite its strengths, this study has several limitations. First, the data are based on self-reported responses, which may be affected by social desirability bias or underreporting due to the sensitivity of the topic. Second, the questionnaire did not investigate the context or motivations behind the creation of deep nudes, nor the identity of the individuals depicted. Further qualitative research is needed to explore these dimensions and provide a more nuanced understanding of the behavior. Additionally, although the sample is large and diverse, it was not randomly selected, and participation was voluntary—this introduces the risk of selection bias and limits the generalizability of the findings beyond the Czech context.

The broader implications of the study highlight the urgent need for comprehensive prevention strategies at the intersection of education, law, and technology. Schools, families, and policymakers must work together to enhance media literacy, promote digital ethics, and provide robust support systems for victims. Legal frameworks, such as the EU AI Act and the forthcoming directive on combating violence against women, are crucial steps forward, but further harmonization and enforcement across member states remain necessary. Technological countermeasures, including detection tools and stricter access controls to AI generators, should be developed in tandem with education and legislation.

Ultimately, combating the misuse of AI to generate non-consensual sexual content requires a holistic approach that addresses not only the technological enablers but also the social and psychological roots of such behavior. As the capabilities of AI continue to evolve, so must our collective responsibility to ensure that these tools are used ethically and do not become instruments of harm - especially for the most vulnerable members of society.

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